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Insights into the subdaily variations in methane, nitrous oxide and carbon dioxide fluxes from upland tropical tree stems

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Complete List of Authors:	Bréchet, Laëticia; University of Antwerp Faculty of Sciences, Biology; Ecologie des Forêts de Guyane, INRAE Salomon, Roberto; Universidad Politécnica de Madrid , Dpto. Sistemas y Recursos Naturales Machacova, Katerina; Global Change Research Institute Czech Academy of Sciences, Department of Ecosystem Trace Gas Exchange Stahl, Clement; ECOFOG, Ecophysiology Burban, Benoit; ECOFOG, Ecophysiology Goret, Jean-Yves; ECOFOG, Ecophysiology Steppe, Kathy; Ghent University, Laboratory of Plant Ecology; Bonal, Damien; INRA Département Ecologie des Forêts Prairies et milieux Aquatiques, UMR SILVA Janssens, Ivan; Universiteit Antwerpen, Department of Biology
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The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

For Peer Review

1 **For New Phytologist**

2

3 **WORKING TITLE: Biophysical control of methane, nitrous oxide and carbon dioxide fluxes from**
4 **tropical tree stems**

5 **TITLE: Insights into the subdaily variations in methane, nitrous oxide and carbon dioxide fluxes from**
6 **upland tropical tree stems**

7

8 Laëtitia M. Bréchet^{1,2,*}, Roberto L. Salomón^{3,4}, Katerina Machacova⁵, Clément Stahl¹, Benoît Burban¹,
9 Jean-Yves Goret¹, Kathy Steppe⁴, Damien Bonal⁶, Ivan A. Janssens²

10

11 ¹INRAE, UMR EcoFoG, CNRS, Cirad, AgroParisTech, Université des Antilles, Université de Guyane,
12 97310 Kourou, France

13 ²Centre of Excellence PLECO (Plants and Ecosystems), Department of Biology, University of Antwerp,
14 Universiteitsplein 1, B-2610 Wilrijk, Belgium

15 ³Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. Departamento de Sistemas y Recursos Naturales. FORESCENT
16 research group, 28040 Madrid, Spain

17 ⁴Laboratory of Plant Ecology, Department of Plants and Crops, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering,
18 Ghent University, 9000 Ghent, Belgium

19 ⁵Department of Ecosystem Trace Gas Exchange, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech
20 Academy of Sciences, Belidla 4a, CZ-60300 Brno, Czech Republic

21 ⁶Université de Lorraine, AgroParisTech, INRAE, UMR Silva, F-54000 Nancy, France

22 *email: laeti.brechet@gmail.com; phone number: +594 594 32 92 91; [https://orcid.org/0000-0002-](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2744-8820)
23 2744-8820

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Materials and Methods	2558
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26 ABSTRACT

27 • Recent studies have shown that stem fluxes, although highly variable among trees, can alter
28 the strength of the methane (CH₄) sink or nitrous oxide (N₂O) source in some forests, but the patterns
29 and magnitudes of these fluxes remain unclear. This study investigated the drivers of subdaily
30 variations in CH₄, N₂O and carbon dioxide (CO₂) fluxes.

31 • CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes were measured continuously in individual stems of two tree species
32 and surrounding soils using an automated chamber system in an upland tropical forest. Subdaily
33 variations in these fluxes were compared with environmental and stem physiological measurements
34 under contrasting soil water conditions.

35 • The results showed that physiological and climatic drivers (sap flow, vapour pressure deficit,
36 tree water deficit, temperature) only partially explained the subdaily variations. Stem CH₄ and CO₂
37 emissions and N₂O uptake varied with soil water content, time of day and tree, and were not closely
38 related to or controlled by soil surface fluxes.

39 • Our study contributes to the general understanding of the environmental regulation of stem
40 greenhouse gas fluxes and shows that additional variables (e.g. internal gas concentrations, wood
41 colonising microorganisms, wood density) may account for the remaining unexplained variability in
42 stem fluxes, highlighting the need for further studies.

43

44 KEY WORDS

45 Carbon dioxide, flux, methane, nitrous oxide, soil, subdaily variations, tree stem, upland tropical forest

46

47 INTRODUCTION

48 Atmospheric methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O), two greenhouse gases, are the second and
49 third most important contributors to global warming after carbon dioxide (CO₂; Stocker *et al.*, 2013),
50 and their concentrations in the atmosphere are rising rapidly (Nisbet *et al.*, 2019). Forest ecosystems,
51 which account for approximately 30% of the Earth's land surface (FAO 2010) and represent the largest
52 carbon stock of all terrestrial ecosystems, play an important role in regulating and mitigating global
53 climate change (Pan *et al.*, 2011). In addition, forest ecosystems cover most continental regions, and
54 compared to agricultural soils, forest soils generally act as large CO₂ sinks and small net sinks for the
55 potent greenhouse gas CH₄, while they are either very small sinks or emitters of the even more potent

56 greenhouse gas N₂O. Overall, forests, in particular upland forests generally have a net greenhouse gas
57 mitigation effect (Megonigal & Guenther, 2008; Welch 2018).

58 Some plant and microbial processes produce (e.g. autotrophic and heterotrophic respiration,
59 denitrification, nitrification, and methanogenesis) and consume (e.g. photosynthesis, denitrification;
60 oxidation) greenhouse gases in and at the soil-atmosphere interface. Their rate and magnitude are
61 constrained by biotic and abiotic factors (Mosier *et al.*, 2004). Among these, vegetation type (Veber
62 *et al.*, 2018) and soil water content (Courtois *et al.*, 2018; Bréchet *et al.*, 2019), temperature (Holland
63 *et al.*, 2000), microbial abundance and activity (Gray 2014), and nutrient availability (especially
64 nitrogen and phosphorus; Courtois *et al.*, 2018; Bréchet *et al.*, 2019) can influence greenhouse gas
65 fluxes (Fig. 1).

66 Certain evidence now makes it clear that all biological forest surfaces have the potential to
67 exchange greenhouse gases. These include previously ignored CH₄ and N₂O sources and sinks in plants,
68 especially tree stems, which can contribute significantly to the net ecosystem exchange of N₂O and
69 CH₄, in addition to the more extensively studied CO₂. Trees can 1) take up CH₄ and N₂O from the soil
70 through their root system and transport them to the atmosphere via the transpiration stream, the
71 aerenchyma tissue or enlarged intercellular spaces (Welch *et al.*, 2018; Machacova *et al.*, 2021;
72 Bréchet *et al.*, 2021); 2) produce N₂O and CH₄ directly in woody tissues (Jeffrey *et al.*, 2021b; Feng *et al.*,
73 2022); 3) take up N₂O and CH₄ from the atmosphere by an as yet unknown mechanism (Machacova
74 *et al.*, 2021, 2024; Bréchet *et al.*, 2021); and 4) alter the nitrogen and carbon turnover processes in
75 the adjacent soil (Menyailo & Hungate, 2005). All these possible pathways make it difficult to
76 disentangle the mechanisms by which greenhouse gases, (in particular understudied CH₄ and N₂O),
77 are emitted or taken up by the stems of living trees, thus hindering their accurate estimation.

78 Recent studies have shown that stem fluxes, although highly variable among trees (Barba *et al.*,
79 2019b), can potentially alter the strength of the CH₄ sink (Gauci *et al.*, 2024; Pitz & Megonigal, 2017)
80 or the N₂O source (Machacova *et al.*, 2021, 2024) in montane forests, with implications for their
81 greenhouse gas budgets. It is therefore essential to quantify the patterns and magnitudes of these
82 poorly understood fluxes.

83 Efforts have been made to identify subdaily variations, their associated drivers and the origins of
84 CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes in tree stems. In 2017, Pitz and Megonigal suggested studying sap flow
85 simultaneously with stem CH₄ fluxes to explain the subdaily patterns observed in *Liriodendron*
86 *tulipifera* tree stems in an upland temperate forest. More recent studies have discussed the
87 relationship between sap flow and stem CH₄ emissions at subdaily and seasonal time scales (Barba *et al.*
88 *et al.*, 2019b; Jeffrey *et al.*, 2020) for worldwide forest ecosystems. As for stem CO₂ emissions (Teskey *et al.*
89 *et al.*, 2008; Aubrey & Teskey, 2021; Salomon *et al.*, 2024), the physical processes involved in CH₄

90 transport within the tree include the dissolution of the CH₄ produced in the soil - in water, which can
91 then be absorbed by the roots, transported through the xylem with the sap solution and emitted
92 through the stem by effervescence (Barba *et al.*, 2019a). This link between below-ground microbial
93 processes and above-ground CH₄ emissions may also occur for N₂O, although this remains to be
94 demonstrated. In addition, day-night variations in stem CH₄ fluxes are sometimes, but not always
95 (Pangala *et al.*, 2014; Terazawa *et al.*, 2015; Schindler *et al.*, 2021), explained by thermal changes in
96 the trees in temperate (Barba *et al.*, 2019b) and subtropical lowland forests (Jeffrey *et al.*, 2020).

97 On the other hand, subdaily variations in greenhouse gas fluxes can also be explained either by the
98 diffusivity of the bark (and deeper tissues) or by the cryptogams associated with the bark, which may
99 harbour uncharacterised microbiomes and contribute to stem greenhouse gas exchange (Machacova
100 *et al.*, 2017, 2021; Yip *et al.*, 2019; Jeffrey *et al.*, 2021a, b; Putkinen *et al.*, 2021). In addition, tree stems
101 can also produce CH₄ by non-microbial processes in the woody tissues via abiotic aerobic pathways
102 from plant compounds such as pectin, lignin, cellulose, methionine and ascorbic acid originating
103 during cell wall assembly and the synthesis of structural components (Keppler *et al.*, 2006; Viganò *et al.*,
104 2008). This non-microbial source of CH₄ within the stem also depends on tree characteristics, and
105 tree and stand health status. Stem wood can be infected and degrade, thus producing CH₄, as
106 previously described in studies that found elevated CH₄ concentrations in the xylem (Mukhin &
107 Voronin, 2011; Covey *et al.*, 2012; Wang *et al.*, 2016, 2017; Jeffrey *et al.*, 2021a; Machacova *et al.*,
108 2023). Moisan *et al.*, (2024) reviewed which tree traits can influence CH₄ transport and modify the
109 availability of CH₄ and how; for example, modifying the habitat for methanogens and methanotrophs
110 alters net stem CH₄ fluxes.

111 In tropical forests, the soil is one of the largest sources of N₂O (Werner *et al.*, 2007) and is also an
112 active sink for CH₄ (Dutaur & Verchot, 2007). Globally, tropical forests are estimated to emit 1.27 kg
113 N₂O ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Zhuang *et al.*, 2012) and take up 3.33 kg CH₄ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Dutaur & Verchot, 2007). They
114 sequester about 10 % of the total atmospheric CO₂ via photosynthesis (Malhi & Phillips, 2004, and
115 account for about 30 % of the world's soil carbon stocks (Jobbágy & Jackson, 2000).

116 There is increasing interest in greenhouse gas exchanges in tropical wetlands like the Amazon
117 floodplain (Graffmann *et al.*, 2008; Pangala *et al.*, 2017) and in mangrove swamps (Kreuzwieser *et al.*,
118 2003; Krithika *et al.*, 2008), but data on the contribution of tropical forests located on freely drained
119 (i.e. only temporarily water-logged under anaerobic conditions) upland soils is still too insufficient to
120 quantify (Bréchet *et al.*, 2021; Gauci *et al.*, 2024; Welch *et al.*, 2018). Although upland tropical forests
121 are not generally considered to be major sources of CH₄ and N₂O emissions, they cover more land area
122 than tropical wetlands (Pan *et al.*, 2013). In addition, for global CH₄ and N₂O budgets, Earth system
123 models and carbon accounting policies, it is generally assume that the role of upland forests can be

124 determined by measuring the rate of greenhouse gas fluxes at the soil surface only; the above-ground
125 components of forest ecosystems are rarely considered. One knowledge gap we aim to address in the
126 present study is how tree physiology and environmental drivers control stem greenhouse gas fluxes
127 on a subdaily time scale in upland tropical forests under limited and non-limited soil water conditions.

128 In 2021, we set up an automated system to continuously measure greenhouse gas fluxes in both
129 soils and tree stems at a high temporal (subhourly) resolution (Bréchet *et al.*, 2021) in a tropical
130 rainforest in French Guiana. Our system operated successfully over 19 months, and in the present
131 study, we examine the subdaily patterns of CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes from individual stems of different
132 tropical tree species and from their surrounding soils under contrasted soil water conditions (very dry
133 and very wet conditions). We investigate the drivers modulating subdaily variations in these fluxes. To
134 do so, we conducted a detailed investigation of the relationships between subdaily CH₄, N₂O and CO₂
135 fluxes and different drivers, related to tree physiology (e.g. sap flow, irreversible stem growth, tree
136 water deficit, CO₂ dissolved in the xylem sap) and environmental conditions (e.g. soil and stem
137 temperature, soil and stem water content, vapour pressure deficit (VPD)), which show substantial day-
138 night variations under tropical forest conditions. By comparing days with contrasting soil water
139 availability during the 19-month study period, we tested the following hypotheses (based on the
140 assumptions shown in Fig. 1):

141 **H1.** Tropical tree stems exhibit subdaily patterns for CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes,

142 **H2.** The magnitude of the subdaily variations in stem CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes is reduced under
143 severe soil water stress and the consequent downregulation of tree physiological activity (i.e. root
144 uptake, photosynthesis, transpiration) and microbial activity in the soil and woody tissues,

145 **H3.** Subdaily variations in stem CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes are regulated by tree transpiration,
146 assuming that the gas fluxes measured result from physiological and microbial activity occurring
147 underneath the measurement point on the stem, and from below-ground processes and gas
148 transport. In addition, we postulated that stem CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes could not be predicted from
149 soil CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O fluxes.

150

Biotic and abiotic drivers regulating subdaily variations in greenhouse gas (CH_4 , N_2O , CO_2) fluxes in trees

151

152 **Fig. 1** Schematic representation of the biotic production and consumption pathways for methane (CH_4), nitrous oxide (N_2O) and carbon dioxide (CO_2) in soils
 153 and tree woody tissues. These biotic pathways include methanotrophy, methanogenesis, nitrification, denitrification, nitrifier denitrification, and dissimilatory
 154 nitrate reduction to ammonium. The abiotic drivers include solar radiation, air temperature and humidity. Net fluxes (red arrows) for CH_4 and N_2O measured
 155 at stem surfaces are the product of the balance between in situ CH_4 and N_2O emissions (production) and uptake (consumption), while for CO_2 , emissions are
 156 mainly produced by the respiratory activity of woody tissue. Potential subdaily variations in CH_4 , N_2O and CO_2 fluxes in tree stems (assumptions: A1-3c)
 157 depending on physiological and environmental variables.

158 MATERIALS AND METHODS

159 1. Study site and experimental design

160 The Paracou experimental site is located in the undisturbed Amazon rainforest of French Guiana,
161 in the Guiana Shield, French Guiana, South America (5°50'N, 52°55'W). The forest has a dominant
162 canopy height of 35 m, a tree density of 620 trees ha⁻¹ (diameter at breast height (DBH) > 10 cm) and
163 between 150 and 200 species ha⁻¹. In this diverse forest, tree species mainly belong to the
164 *Lecythidaceae*, *Fabaceae*, *Sapotaceae* and *Chrysobalanaceae* families (Gourlet-Fleury *et al.*, 2004;
165 Bonal *et al.*, 2008). The canopy is dense, with a plant area index of about 7.0 m² m⁻², which limits the
166 amount of solar radiation reaching the ground and, thus, reduces variations in soil temperature
167 throughout the year (Bonal *et al.*, 2008). The mean annual air temperature for the period 2004 - 2015
168 was 25.7 ± 0.1 °C, and the mean annual precipitation was c. 3102 ± 70 mm yr⁻¹, with a heavy rainy
169 season from December to July and a dry season from August to November during which precipitation
170 is typically < 100 mm month⁻¹ (Aguilos *et al.*, 2019). The soils are Acrisols (FAO - ISRIC - ISSS, 1998) with
171 pockets of sandy Ultisols developed over a Precambrian metamorphic formation composed of schist
172 and sandstone (Bonal *et al.*, 2008). On average, the soils are nutrient-poor, acidic (pH = 4.2), sandy
173 (72% sand and 12% clay), and contain 2.2%, 0.15% and 1.8 mg kg⁻¹ of total carbon, total nitrogen, and
174 available phosphorus (Bray-P), respectively (Van Langenhove *et al.*, 2021).

175 2. Measuring net CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes in tree stems and soils

176 The greenhouse gas fluxes, i.e. CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O, were continuously monitored from two tree
177 stems ($n = 2$) and two soil locations ($n = 2$) approximately two meters away from each instrumented
178 tree, on top of a small 40-m high hill in the upland forest part of the footprint of the Guyaflux flux
179 tower at the Paracou site (Epron *et al.*, 2006). The two selected trees were dominant canopy trees, an
180 *Eperua falcata* and a *Lecythis poiteaui* (hereafter Ef and Lp, respectively) with a DBH of 0.47 and 0.59
181 m, for Lp and Ef, respectively (Table 1). The trees were growing on hypoferralic soils with deep vertical
182 drainage and a deep water table. We measured stem and soil CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O fluxes from October
183 15th 2019 to June 08th 2021, thus encompassing two wet seasons and three dry seasons, each
184 characterised by a total precipitation below 100 mm. The study period was concomitant with part of
185 the 2021 La Niña event.

186 We used the fully automated closed dynamic chamber system described in Bréchet *et al.*, (2021)
187 for the continuous measurement of the soil and stem greenhouse gas fluxes. The soil-flux system
188 consists of commercially available long-term soil chambers (LI-8100-104; Li-Cor Biosciences, Lincoln,
189 NE, USA) equipped with quick-fit bulkhead tube fittings connected to a multiplexer (LI-8150; Li-Cor
190 Biosciences, Lincoln, NE, USA) and two gas analysers: 1) an infrared gas analyser (IRGA LI-8100A; Li-

191 Cor Biosciences, Lincoln, NE, USA) to measure the dry mole fractions of CO₂ and 2) a cavity ring-down
192 spectroscopy (CRDS) analyser (G2308; Picarro Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA) connected to an external
193 recirculation pump (A0702; Picarro Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA) to measure the wet mole fractions of
194 CO₂ and the dry mole fractions of CH₄ and N₂O. Additional information on the soil flux system can be
195 found in Courtois *et al.*, (2019). This automated system had two drawbacks that limited the spatial
196 coverage of the measurements to two trees: the power supply was only available at the flux tower
197 nearby, and the maximum distance between the automated chambers and the gas analysers was 15
198 m.

199 The stem flux system consisted of two custom-built chambers, each covering a stem area of 0.054
200 m², made of a flexible, gas-impermeable, rectangular polycarbonate plastic sheet sealed with
201 expanded neoprene strips and non-caustic silicone to prevent air leakage. The stem chambers,
202 installed at 130 cm height and covered with aluminium foil to prevent photosynthesis by any woody
203 tissues or cryptogamic organisms growing on the bark, which could have significantly affected the
204 stem CO₂ flux (Steppe *et al.*, 2015; De Roo *et al.*, 2020). The total air volume of the tree - stem- and
205 soil-chamber (including the 15 m tube) systems was 0.0011 and 0.0058 m³, respectively. In contrast
206 to the automated soil chambers, the stem chambers remained permanently closed and were
207 connected to a diaphragm vacuum air pump (KNF N86; Neuberger GmbH, Germany), for continuous
208 air renewal outside measurement periods. In the flush mode between measurements, the flow rate
209 between the chamber and the multiplexer was ~3 L min⁻¹ and ~1.7 L min⁻¹ in the subsampling lines
210 connecting the multiplexer to the two gas analysers, as recommended by the manufacturers. The
211 multiplexer was programmed for specific measurement cycles, including purges 15 s before and 45 s
212 after the sampling period to flush the tubing and return to ambient-air greenhouse gas
213 concentrations, and a dead band of 60 s to avoid potential measurement errors due to pressure
214 changes and time lags along the chamber - tubing - analyser circuit following chamber or solenoid
215 valve closure. A detailed description of the combined soil - tree stem flux system can be found in
216 Bréchet *et al.*, (2021).

217 All greenhouse gas fluxes were calculated with the SOILFLUXPRO software (v.4.2; Li-Cor
218 Biosciences, Lincoln, NE, USA) using the raw data recorded by both analysers for 1400 s. Based on the
219 change in greenhouse gas concentrations within the chamber, for stem chambers, fluxes were
220 computed for CO₂ using the first 350 s and for CH₄ and N₂O the first 1400 s; for soil chambers 90 s
221 were used for CO₂ and 1400 s for CH₄ and N₂O.

222 After calculating the fluxes, the standard stem- and soil-greenhouse gas quality check procedures
223 (Bréchet *et al.*, 2021; Courtois *et al.*, 2019) were implemented and flux data for all three gases were
224 discarded if the CO₂ flux had an insufficiently high R² (< 0.90), an initial concentration greater than 900

225 ppm, or a flux value outside the range of 0.10 to 30.00 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. This assumption was that poor-
 226 quality CO_2 data signalled problems with the measurement set-up, which would also generate poor-
 227 quality values for CH_4 and N_2O . If no corresponding CO_2 data was recorded by the infrared gas analyser,
 228 CH_4 and N_2O fluxes were discarded and categorised as not available (NA hereafter) because in this
 229 case we could not properly assess the performance of the system. For the remaining CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O
 230 fluxes, the best fit between exponential and linear regressions of the concentrations over time was
 231 selected based on the R^2 value for each gas and each measurement cycle. This was done because, in
 232 contrast to CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O can be simultaneously produced and consumed in soils and stems, and
 233 low R^2 values are not abnormal under such circumstances. In addition, based on the metrics proposed
 234 by Nickerson (2016), we calculated the minimum detectable fluxes (MDF) suitable for high-resolution
 235 in situ greenhouse gas measurements. For soil fluxes, MDF values were 2.39 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for CO_2 , 0.040
 236 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 2 min and 0.001 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 25 min for CH_4 , and 0.100 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 2 min and
 237 0.002 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 25 min for N_2O . For stem fluxes, MDF values were 0.299 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for CO_2 ,
 238 0.005 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 2 min and 0.0001 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 25 min for CH_4 , and 0.0125 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 2
 239 min and 0.0003 $\text{nmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 25 min for N_2O . Outliers for each greenhouse gas fluxes were removed
 240 according to the interquartile range criterion. The multiplexer was programmed so that each soil and
 241 stem chamber cycle operated every 3 hours and 40 minutes, thus generating approximately seven
 242 measurements per chamber per day (including chambers with long and short measurements). As
 243 previously reported in Bréchet *et al.*, (2021), CO_2 fluxes measured with the IRGA Li-8100A and the
 244 CRDS G2308 analysers were in good agreement both for soil and stems (Fig. S1). In addition, all fluxes
 245 are expressed per m^2 (of stem area for stem fluxes, and of soil area for soil fluxes).

246 3. Environmental measurements

247 Our experimental setup was located 50 m from the Gyaflux tower (Bonal *et al.*, 2008), where
 248 meteorological measurements are taken at ground level, at canopy level and at the top of a 55-m-high
 249 self-supporting metal flux tower, approximately 20 m above the canopy. Soil temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$; CS107;
 250 Campbell Scientific Inc., Logan, UT, USA) and soil water content (SWC, %; CS650, Campbell Scientific
 251 Inc.) were measured at a depth of 0 - 5 cm. Vapour pressure deficit above the canopy (VPD, kPa) was
 252 calculated from air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and relative humidity (%; HMP155, Vaisala, Helsinki, Finland).
 253 The data for all of the environmental variables mentioned above were collected at 1 min intervals
 254 with CR23X, CR1000 or CR3000 dataloggers (Campbell Scientific Inc., Logan, UT, USA) and compiled as
 255 30 min averages.

256 4. Tree stem physiological measurements

257 To relate stem greenhouse gas fluxes to tree stem water, growth and respiration activities,
 258 variations in stem diameter, sap flow and xylem CO_2 concentrations were continuously monitored

259 during the study period in the two selected trees. Variations in stem diameter (μm) were measured
260 with automated, high-precision point dendrometers (ZN11-T-WP; Natkon, Oetwil am See,
261 Switzerland). The dendrometers were anchored to the stem with stainless steel rods at breast height
262 on the side of the trunk opposite the stem chambers. The rhytidome was carefully removed with a
263 small brush to avoid damaging the living tissue and the dendrometers were placed against the inner
264 bark. The dendrometers were individually calibrated at the time of installation.

265 Sap flux density was measured with Granier-type heat dissipation probes (UP GmbH, Ibbenbüren,
266 Germany; Granier 1985) inserted into each tree stem at 130 cm in height, approximately 10 cm from
267 the dendrometer. Each probe had two 32 mm long gauge stainless steel needles, inside 2.1-mm-wide
268 aluminium tubes to improve thermal conductivity, which were inserted into the xylem tissue. The two
269 probes were sealed with waterproof rubber and carefully covered with semi-rigid transparent plastic
270 and aluminium foil to prevent distorted readings due to rain, direct solar radiation and high
271 temperatures. Tree sap flow rate (g s^{-1}) was estimated as the product of sap flux density and sapwood
272 area (dm^2) determined for each tree from increment cores sampled before the installation of the
273 xylem $[\text{CO}_2]$ sensor (Table 1).

274 Xylem CO_2 concentration in the gaseous phase (xylem $[\text{CO}_2]$, %) was measured with non-dispersive
275 infrared sensors (Vaisala GMP251; Helsinki, Finland), which can withstand a wide range of
276 environmental conditions (including temperatures from $-40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $+60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and have a measurement
277 range from 0 to 20%, commonly observed in tree stems (Teskey *et al.*, 2008; Stutz & Anderson, 2021).
278 In each tree stem, a 32 mm-diameter, 70-mm-deep hole was drilled at a height of 110 cm and at a 45°
279 angle from the dendrometer and sap flow sensor and a perforated polyvinyl chloride (PVC) tube
280 containing the CO_2 probe was inserted but only halfway into the stem (35 mm deep) to leave a head
281 space in the xylem in front of the sensor tip where the CO_2 would be sampled. At the stem surface,
282 the PVC tube and CO_2 probe were sealed together with non-caustic silicone to prevent contamination
283 by the ambient air. The concentrations of CO_2 dissolved in the sap solution (sap $[\text{CO}_2^*]$; $\mu\text{mol CO}_2\text{ L}^{-1}$)
284 were calculated according to Henry's Law (McGuire & Teskey, 2002) based on ancillary measurements
285 of stem temperature and sap pH. Sap pH was measured monthly with a Sentron SI400 pH meter
286 (Sentron Europe BV, Leek, The Netherlands) in xylem sap expressed from canopy branches with a
287 pressure chamber (Table 1). Stem surface temperature was measured with a type-T thermocouple
288 within the dendrometer sensor. All the above-mentioned data were recorded every minute and
289 averaged every 30 min with a CR1000 datalogger (Campbell Scientific Inc., Logan, UT, USA).
290 Additionally, we compared the magnitude of below-ground CO_2 efflux pathways by scaling both soil-
291 derived CO_2 transport from the roots to the stem and soil CO_2 efflux to the same soil unit area (m^2).
292 To do this, we used Aubrey and Teskey's (2009) approach. We estimated the soil surface area occupied

293 by the root system of each monitored tree based on the average stem basal area in the studied stand
 294 (i.e. $31.96 \text{ m}^2 \text{ ha}^{-1}$) and the stem cross-section of each tree, assuming proportionality between the
 295 stem cross-section and the soil surface area occupied by the tree's roots system. We showed the
 296 results for the most complete periods: March 23rd 2021 - April 04th 2021, and July 31st 2020 - August
 297 13th 2020, for Lp and Ef, respectively.

298

299 **Table 1** Diameter at breast height (DBH, 1.30 cm), sapwood thickness and sapwood area at the flux
 300 measurement point, sap pH and estimated root surface of the two studied trees: an *Eperua falcata*
 301 and a *Lecythis poiteaui* in the Paracou forest, French Guiana.

	<i>Lecythis poiteaui</i>	<i>Eperua falcata</i>
DBH (m)	0.47	0.59
Sapwood thickness (mm)	7.50	44.59
Sapwood area (m ²)	0.01	0.05
Sap pH (limited soil water; non-limited soil water period)	[5.89, 5.92]	[6.12, 5.62]
Estimated root surface (%)	0.54	0.85

302

303 5. Data analysis

304 Calculations and statistical analyses, including data cleaning procedures and data visualisation,
 305 were performed under the R statistical programming environment (v.3.6.3; R Core Team, 2020). To
 306 investigate the effect of environmental variables on stem and soil CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O fluxes, we
 307 extracted data from periods with extremes of soil water availability (hereafter "limited soil water" and
 308 "non-limited soil water") (Fig. 2). Limited soil water days occurred during the dry seasons when SWC
 309 fell below a 15% SWC threshold for more than two consecutive days. The non-limited soil water days
 310 represent near-saturated conditions during the wet seasons when a 20% SWC threshold was exceeded
 311 for more than two consecutive days. To obtain comparable atmospheric conditions for both the
 312 limited and non-limited soil water periods, we retained only the sunniest days, i.e. for which the
 313 average of 48 half-hour values fell between 250 and 460 W m⁻².

314 Linear correlations between the CO₂ fluxes measured with the IRGA Li-8100A and the CO₂ fluxes
 315 measured with the CRDS G2308 Picarro were tested to ensure the quality of the flux data ($R^2 > 0.80$).
 316 Raw dendrometer data over the length of the time series were quality-checked and processed with
 317 the "treenetproc" R package (Haeni *et al.*, 2020). Assuming no growth during periods of stem
 318 shrinkage (Zweifel *et al.*, 2016), irreversible growth and stem water deficit were inferred from changes
 319 in stem diameter. Data for CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O fluxes, and physiological (sap flow, radial stem growth,
 320 tree water deficit and xylem [CO₂]) and environmental (stem and soil temperature, SWC and VPD)
 321 variables were tested for normal distribution (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test).

322 To examine subdaily variations in greenhouse gas fluxes, we averaged data over each month at a
 323 one-hour resolution and normalised xylem [CO_2], sap [CO_2^*], and stem and soil CO_2 , CH_4 , N_2O fluxes
 324 to the daily maxima with the “rescale” function from the “scales” R package (Wickham & Seidel, 2020).
 325 We assessed the relationships 1) between soil and stem CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O fluxes, and 2) between stem
 326 CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O fluxes and environmental and physiological variables (that is paired comparisons
 327 with one flux and one environmental or physiological variable at a time) based on Pearson’s pairwise
 328 correlation coefficients generated with the “cor” function from the “stats” R package and the
 329 “ggcorrplot” function from the “ggcorrplot2” R package. We report mean \pm standard deviation and
 330 significant differences at $p < 0.05$ level.

331 At the soil and stem level, we used a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis one-way ANOVA on ranks sums
 332 for multiple comparisons to evaluate the effects of the measurement location and climatic period
 333 (limited vs. non-limited soil water) on the greenhouse gas fluxes.

334

335 RESULTS

336 1. Contrasted climatic periods

337 The study period was characterised by three dry and two wet periods (Fig. 2). During the limited
 338 soil water period, which covered 6.2% of the total study duration, SWC ranged from 10.7% to 15.0%,
 339 whereas during the non-limited soil water period, which covered 9.8% of the total study period, SWC
 340 varied from 20% to 41.2%. Mean air temperature was similar between the limited and non-limited
 341 soil water periods, i.e. 27.5 °C and 26.8 °C, respectively.

342

343 **Fig. 2** Seasonal course from October 15th 2019 to June 08th 2021 of half-hourly mean soil water content
 344 values (0 - 5 cm depth; multi-coloured line) and soil temperature (0 - 5 cm depth; dark grey dots) at

345 the Paracou forest, French Guiana. Different climatic periods, defined based on soil water availability,
346 are indicated by different colours. The two most contrasting periods selected for the study include
347 days with similarly high global radiation conditions (mean of half-hourly values $> 250 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) within
348 the extremely dry (“SDry”) and wet (“SWet”) periods, referred to in the text as the “limited soil water”
349 and “non-limited soil water” periods, respectively, and represented by the blue and red dots on the
350 zero line. Dry seasons are represented by shaded areas.

351

352 2. Subdaily variations in CH_4 , N_2O and CO_2 fluxes

353 We observed subdaily patterns for all greenhouse gas fluxes at both the stem and soil levels (Fig.
354 3). For stems, CH_4 fluxes exhibited large variations over a 24-h cycle. Surprisingly, subdaily patterns
355 were in opposite phase between the two trees Ef and Lp, with peaks observed either at the end or
356 beginning of the day (Fig. 3A, G). The magnitude of these subdaily variations was stronger during the
357 limited soil water period than during the non-limited one (Fig. 3A, G). On the contrary, the subdaily
358 patterns for soil CH_4 fluxes were relatively consistent between the two locations (Fig. 3B, H).

359 For N_2O fluxes, subdaily patterns were comparatively weaker and remarkably consistent between
360 tree stems and soil measurement locations, with no apparent effects of limited or non-limited soil
361 water period. At the stem level, a higher uptake of atmospheric N_2O occurred during the afternoon in
362 the non-limited soil water period (Fig. 3C, I). At the soil level, we observed lower afternoon N_2O
363 emissions during the non-limited period and a higher afternoon N_2O uptake during the limited period
364 (Fig. 3D, J).

365

366 **Fig. 3** Subdaily variations over 24 hours of normalized methane (CH₄; A, B, G, H), nitrous oxide (N₂O;
 367 C, D, I, J) and carbon dioxide (CO₂; E, F, K, L) fluxes in two tree stems (one *Lecythis poiteau* - blue line,
 368 and one *Eperua falcata* - orange line) and their surrounding soils during the limited soil water (A - F)
 369 and non-limited soil water (G - L) periods between 2019 and 2021 in the Paracou forest, French
 370 Guiana. Coloured lines and coloured shaded areas represent the hourly mean \pm the 95% confidence
 371 interval, and vertical grey areas indicate night-time (from 18:00 hr to 06:00 hr). All flux values are
 372 normalized from 0 to 1 to make direct data comparison possible. Small arrows, in the bottom left
 373 corner, illustrate the main flux directions and Figures S5 - S7 the flux magnitudes.

374

375 Subdaily patterns for CO₂ fluxes were similar for both trees, more pronounced during the limited
 376 soil water period than during the non-limited one, and in opposite phase to the surrounding soils (Fig.
 377 3E, F, K, L). Higher emissions of CO₂ from the stems were observed in the afternoon, simultaneous to
 378 the lowest fluxes in the surrounding soils.

379 Figures 4A and 4B show that the sap [CO₂*] in trees Lp and Ef followed an inverse subdaily pattern
 380 to that of sap flow: the subdaily maximum for sap [CO₂*] occurred at night before the onset of sap

381 flow. During the morning, as sap flow increased, the sap [CO₂*] decreased, and its minimum level
 382 coincided approximately with peak sap flow. On the other hand, the subdaily patterns for root-derived
 383 CO₂ passing through the xylem closely followed sap flow patterns and depended on sap [CO₂*] (Fig.
 384 4C, D). Total soil CO₂ flux was higher than the root-derived CO₂ transported through the xylem; only
 385 occasionally, and only in tree Ef, did the latter exceed the soil CO₂ flux. Mean cumulative daily sap
 386 [CO₂*] for Ef and Lp, respectively, was six and 30 times less than mean cumulative soil CO₂ flux (Table
 387 2), indicating that in our tropical forest more of the CO₂ from both autotrophic and heterotrophic
 388 sources diffused from the soil to the atmosphere than was transported via the stem through the
 389 xylem.

390

391 **Table 2** Mean daily total flux of CO₂ transported from the root system through the xylem into the stem
 392 (Xylem), and mean daily total soil CO₂ efflux measured with the soil chamber (Soil) of one *Eperua*
 393 *falcata* and one *Lecythis poiteaui* tree in the Paracou forest, French Guiana. The measurement periods
 394 were March 23rd 2021 - April 04th 2021, and July 31st 2020 - August 13th 2020 for *Lecythis poiteaui*, and
 395 *Eperua falcata*, respectively.

Flux pathway	CO ₂ flux (mol m ⁻² soil area d ⁻¹)	
	<i>Lecythis poiteaui</i>	<i>Eperua falcata</i>
Xylem	0.018	0.134
Soil	0.599	0.810

396

397

398 **Fig. 4** Subdaily variation over several days for total tree sap flow (thin blue or orange lines) and concentrations of CO₂ dissolved in the xylem sap (thick black
399 line) measured in the stems of one *Lecythis poiteau* (A) and one *Eperua falcata* (B) tree. Variations in the corresponding flux of CO₂ transported from the root
400 system through the xylem into the stem (thin black line) and soil CO₂ flux (thick brown line) (C, D) over more than ten days in the Paracou forest, French
401 Guiana. Vertical grey bands indicate night-time (from 18:00 hr to 06:00 hr).

402 3. Subdaily variation in physiological parameters

403 Figure 5 shows the sap flow of the two trees during different water availability periods, together
404 with tree water deficit, stem temperature and xylem [CO₂]. We found clear subdaily patterns these
405 three physiological variables between periods, and large differences in magnitude between the trees.
406 At the seasonal timescale (Fig. S4), sap flow and stem growth were five times higher in Ef than in Lp
407 (Fig. 5, S4A, B). Tree water deficit in Lp deviated from zero and was about three times as high as that
408 of Ef (Fig. 5C, D, S4C), indicating a lack of complete stem refilling overnight for Lp, more evident during
409 the limited soil water period. Xylem [CO₂] varied in the same order of magnitude between the trees
410 and was particularly consistent across periods (Fig. S4D).

411 At the subdaily timescale (Fig 5), sap flow rate, tree water deficit and stem temperature showed
412 typical patterns during the selected periods (Fig. 5A - F), with greater variations observed during the
413 limited soil water period than during the non-limited soil water period. For both Lp and Ef, the subdaily
414 patterns for sap flow, water deficit and stem temperature were consistent, reaching their highest
415 values around midday. Conversely, the subdaily patterns observed for normalised xylem [CO₂]
416 displayed a divergent trend between the two trees (Fig. 5G, H), with peak concentrations either at the
417 beginning of the day for Ef or at the end of the day for Lp.

418

419 **Fig. 5** Subdaily variations over 24 hours in half-hourly values in sap flow rate (A, B), tree water deficit
 420 (C, D), stem surface temperature (E, F), and in the daily maxima of CO₂ concentrations in the xylem
 421 (normalized values) (G, H) in two tree stems (one *Lecythis poiteaui* - blue line, and one *Eperua falcata*
 422 - orange line) during the limited soil water (left panels) and non-limited soil water (right panels)
 423 periods between 2019 and 2021 in the Paracou forest, French Guiana. Coloured lines and coloured
 424 shaded areas represent the hourly mean \pm the 95% confidence interval and vertical grey bands
 425 indicate night-time (from 18:00 hr to 06:00 hr). CO₂ concentrations values are normalized from 0 to 1
 426 to make direct comparison of the data possible.

427 4. Drivers of subdaily variations in stem CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes

428 The correlations between stem and soil CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O fluxes varied depending on the tree, soil
 429 location and water availability period (Fig. 6). An increase in stem CO₂ flux correlated with an increase
 430 in stem N₂O uptake, consistently for Ef during both periods, and for Lp during the limited soil water
 431 period (Fig. 6A, C, D). We observed a relationship between CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes only for Ef during the
 432 limited soil water period (Fig. 6C); this suggests that stem CH₄ emissions did not necessarily follow the
 433 physiological activity of the trees studied. We only found an occasional relationship between stem
 434 and soil CO₂ fluxes for Ef during the non-limited soil water period (Fig. 6A).

435

436

437 **Fig. 6** Heat map based on a correlation matrix between hourly means for nitrous oxide (N₂O; nmol m⁻² s⁻¹), methane (CH₄; nmol m⁻² s⁻¹) and carbon dioxide (CO₂; μmol m⁻² s⁻¹) fluxes from the stem surfaces
 438 of one *Eperua falcata* and one *Lecythis poiteauii* tree and from the surrounding soil during the non-
 439 limited soil water (A, B) and limited soil water (D, E) period between 2019 and 2021 in the Paracou
 440 forest, French Guiana. Warm and cold colours represent positive and negative correlations,
 441 respectively, based on Pearson's correlation test (level of significance: $p < 0.05$). The flux units are
 442 expressed per m², related to m⁻² of stem area and m⁻² of soil area.

444

445 Environmental and physiological variables correlated as expected (Fig. 7A - D). Strong positive
446 correlations were found between sap flow, tree water deficit, air temperature and VPD, consistently
447 for both water availability periods and both trees. High sap flow occurred when VPD and temperature
448 were high, especially during the non-limited soil water period. Only for Lp during the limited soil water
449 period did tree water deficit fail to correlate with sap flow, temperature or VPD. Correlations between
450 stem CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ fluxes and environmental and physiological variables during the two different
451 soil-water periods were tree- and period-dependent (Fig. 7). Increases in sap flow, tree water deficit,
452 air temperature and VPD were often associated with increases in stem N₂O uptake (Fig. 7A - C) for
453 both trees, and with a decreases in stem CH₄ emissions for Lp (Fig. 7B - D). Stem CO₂ emissions for Ef
454 partially increased with sap flow, tree water deficit, air temperature and VPD during the non-limited
455 soil water period.
456

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457

458 **Fig. 7** Heat map based on a correlation matrix between hourly means for stem fluxes of nitrous oxide (N₂O; nmol m⁻² s⁻¹), methane (CH₄; nmol m⁻² s⁻¹) and
 459 carbon dioxide (CO₂; μmol m⁻² s⁻¹), and environmental and tree physiological drivers, including tree stem water deficit (Water deficit; μm), sap flow rate (g s⁻¹)
 460 ¹), stem temperature (temperature; °C) and vapour pressure deficit (VPD; kPa), for one *Eperua falcata* and one *Lecythis poiteaui* tree during the non-limited
 461 soil water (A, B) and limited soil water (C, D) period between 2019 and 2021 in the Paracou forest, French Guiana. Warm and cold colours represent positive
 462 and negative correlations, respectively, based on Pearson's correlation test (level of significance: $p < 0.05$).

463 **DISCUSSION**

464 Our results show that the stems of the selected trees predominantly emitted CH₄ and CO₂ and
465 consumed N₂O throughout the study period, while the surrounding soils consistently emitted CO₂ and,
466 depending on the time of year, either emitted or consumed CH₄ and N₂O (Fig. S6 - S8), confirming the
467 preliminary data from the same study site (Bréchet *et al.*, 2021). Overall, CH₄ and CO₂ fluxes per m² of
468 stem area were ten times lower, and N₂O fluxes up to twenty times lower, than the respective fluxes
469 per m² of soil area.

470

471 **1. Stem CH₄ fluxes in tropical trees: subdaily patterns and drivers**

472 Our study is the first to reveal subdaily patterns for stem CH₄ emissions in tropical trees, thus
473 confirming H1. Our results corroborate studies conducted on temperate forests (Pitz & Magonigal,
474 2017; Barba *et al.*, 2019b; Takahashi *et al.*, 2022; Anttila *et al.*, 2023). In an upland temperate forest,
475 a subdaily pattern for stem CH₄ fluxes was clearly observed in *L. tulipifera* (Pitz & Magonigal, 2017),
476 but the data were limited to only three days. The authors suggested that soil might also be a source
477 of CH₄ and that transpiration might be a potential driver of stem CH₄ fluxes in some tree species.
478 However, the lack of relationships with SWC or groundwater depth suggested that the stem CH₄
479 emissions in these trees was of microbial origin from the woody tissue. Other studies in upland
480 temperate forests have similarly identified transpiration and temperature as potential positive drivers
481 of stem CH₄ fluxes at subdaily timescales (Barba *et al.*, 2019b). While only one tree was measured by
482 Barba *et al.*, (2019b), Pitz and Magonigal (2017) monitored two trees with automated flux chambers
483 and observed striking differences in subdaily patterns for stem CH₄ emissions, similar to what we
484 observed in our study (Fig. 3A).

485 Consistent with H2, the magnitude of the subdaily patterns for stem CH₄ emissions for Ef and Lp
486 varied with contrasted soil water conditions, suggesting a relationship with sap flow, which is strongly
487 correlated with soil water levels. Interestingly, however, this relationship was opposite in phase for
488 our two trees and was only significant for Lp at the water availability scale.

489 In our study, diurnal variations in Lp stem CH₄ emissions were significantly but negatively
490 correlated with VPD, temperature, sap flow and tree water deficit, regardless of seasonal water
491 availability period (confirming H3). One possible explanation could be that during the night no
492 transpiration takes place so [CH₄] accumulates, and increases its radial diffusion. During daytime, [CH₄]
493 is carried away in the transpiration stream, reducing its radial diffusion, which explains the 60% diurnal
494 decrease in CH₄ emissions we observed during transpiration hours. In addition to the particularly low
495 solubility of CH₄ in water (23 - 40 mg L⁻¹ water at 0 - 20 °C), about 80 times lower than that of CO₂,

496 warmer temperatures during the day may further reduce CH₄ solubilisation in the sap solution,
497 enhancing CH₄ radial diffusion. This would explain our observations for Ef, but not for Lp. Takahashi *et*
498 *al.*, (2022) found, on the contrary, that the diurnal increase in CH₄ emission was almost synchronous
499 with an increase in sap flow in an *Alnus japonica* tree from a riparian wetland in a temperate forest in
500 Japan.

501 Contrary to tree Lp, no similar relationships were found for the Ef tree stem, which showed
502 subdaily patterns for CH₄ emissions similar to recent modelling results (Anttila *et al.*, 2023), with higher
503 emissions in the afternoon when transpiration and tree physiological activity are maximal. Following
504 the reasoning of Pitz and Megonigal (2017), Takahashi *et al.*, (2022) proposes a simple model in which
505 the total CH₄ emission rate consists of “sap flux-dependent” and “sap flux-independent” components.
506 There is still no consensus as to the exact origin of stem CH₄ as the origin seems to be highly dependent
507 on the tree. Our data cannot resolve whether stem-emitted CH₄ is mainly produced underground and
508 bypasses the methanotrophic upper soil layers, or whether it is produced by methanogenic
509 microorganisms living in the woody tissues or by abiotic aerobic pathways in the wood.

510 The soils surrounding the two studied trees were mainly CH₄ consumers in both limited and non-
511 limited soil water periods, but to a different extent. The upland soils we studied were hypoferralic
512 acrisols characterised by deep vertical drainage (Epron *et al.*, 2006). It is likely that these well-aerated
513 soils provide aerobic conditions where CH₄ oxidation by methanotrophs is dominant (Smith *et al.*,
514 2003). In these soils, SWC and temperature are important drivers of CH₄ oxidation (Werner *et al.*,
515 2007; Courtois *et al.*, 2018; Bréchet *et al.*, in review). It therefore appears that the CH₄ emissions from
516 the Ef and Lp stems were not closely related to, or controlled by, soil surface CH₄ fluxes or parameters
517 directly or indirectly related to soil CH₄.

518 2. Stem N₂O fluxes in tropical trees: subdaily patterns and drivers

519 The stems of the two tropical trees we studied showed weak N₂O uptake on average with
520 significant subdaily variations, supporting H1 and confirming the first observations made on a single
521 tree in the same tropical forest (Bréchet *et al.*, 2021). However, contrary to H2, the trees showed
522 similar N₂O patterns for both soil water periods, suggesting a water-independent potential for N₂O
523 uptake in tropical trees at the seasonal timescale. Studies investigating N₂O exchanges in tree stems
524 are still very limited, and most present trees as N₂O emitters (Machacova *et al.*, 2016; Wen *et al.*,
525 2017). The evidence of trees' ability to absorb N₂O from the atmosphere remains sparse and the
526 phenomenon globally unexplained. N₂O uptake by stems was previously observed in European beech
527 (Machacova *et al.*, 2017, 2024), but this was ascribed to the activity of cryptogamic stem covers.
528 Thereafter, similar cryptogamic stem covers sampled on different tropical tree species (Machacova *et*
529 *al.*, 2021) and analysed under in vivo low-light conditions to simulate forest understory conditions

530 identified these photoautotrophic organisms as consistent N₂O consumers. The N₂O uptake rates of
531 these cryptogam assemblies, combining lichens, mosses and algae, were comparable to the uptake
532 rates of the tree stems measured in situ (Machacova *et al.*, 2017, 2021), supporting the hypothesis of
533 N₂O uptake by cryptogamic organisms. Furthermore, in their study on European beech, Machacova *et*
534 *al.*, (2017) observed that N₂O consumption rates were closely related to the respiratory CO₂ fluxes of
535 both trees and cryptogams, suggesting a link between N₂O consumption and the physiological activity
536 of trees and cryptogams. In a boreal forest, seasonal stem N₂O fluxes also followed tree physiological
537 activity (Machacova *et al.*, 2019). However, photoautotrophic cryptogams could not explain the N₂O
538 sink in our study, as the stem chambers were darkened and remained in place throughout the study
539 period. We also observed a daytime increase in both stem CO₂ emissions and stem N₂O uptake,
540 suggesting either a direct link between stem N₂O uptake and tree physiological activity or their
541 common response of the same environmental drivers (temperature and VPD). Our results support H3,
542 which follows this reasoning: our stems showed higher N₂O uptake during the day when tree
543 transpiration was highest.

544 The N₂O fluxes in the soil around our two studied trees were characterised by a remarkable spatial
545 differentiation; they were either N₂O emitters or N₂O consumers, depending on the soil water
546 conditions. In the upland soils we studied, N₂O consumption predominated during the driest period,
547 whereas N₂O production predominated during the wettest period, when external nitrogen inputs from
548 decomposing litter and canopy throughfall commonly increase (Fig. S7). In these soils, available
549 phosphorus, the carbon-to-nitrogen ratio and SWC are important drivers of soil N₂O fluxes (Courtois
550 *et al.*, 2018; Bréchet *et al.*, in review). As for stem N₂O fluxes, we found consistent subdaily patterns
551 for soil N₂O fluxes, regardless of location and seasonal period. However, similar to CH₄ fluxes decreases
552 in N₂O uptake from the Ef and Lp stems did not appear to be related to, or controlled by, soil N₂O
553 fluxes, thus supporting H3.

554 3. Stem CO₂ fluxes in tropical trees: subdaily patterns and drivers

555 In support of H1, stem CO₂ fluxes (or effluxes) presented a clear subdaily pattern, with increased
556 stem CO₂ effluxes of similar magnitude during the daytime in Ef and Lp. However, this pattern was
557 attenuated during the non-limited soil water period, contrary to H2, which predicted that subdaily
558 variability in stem CO₂ emissions would be attenuated under drought stress. The relatively mild
559 drought stress typically experienced by trees in tropical climates may explain this lack of seasonal
560 response to water availability.

561 A strong (20 - 50%) increase in CO₂ flux was observed during the day as opposed to the night. In
562 accordance with H3, the diurnal increase in CO₂ flux can be attributed to the well-known
563 thermoregulatory mechanism of respiratory metabolism, which allows us to estimate the

564 temperature sensitivity of stem CO₂ emissions in tropical trees (e.g. Yang *et al.*, 2012). Nevertheless,
565 our results are inconsistent with previous studies of several individual trees under similar conditions
566 at sites in the Amazon, where higher CO₂ fluxes were found during the night than during the day, and
567 where CO₂ fluxes fell with the onset of xylem sap flow and increasing air temperatures in the early
568 morning (Kunert 2018; Jardine *et al.*, 2022). These exceptional subdaily patterns challenge the primary
569 thermal effect on respiration, and could be attributed to daytime depressions in (temperature-
570 normalized) stem CO₂ flux rates ascribed to CO₂ transport through the xylem, or to low cell-turgor
571 pressure (Saveyn *et al.*, 2007; Steppe *et al.*, 2015; Salomon *et al.*, 2018), which can occasionally drive
572 subdaily patterns of stem CO₂ efflux in tropical regions with limited day-night thermal fluctuations. In
573 our study, the subdaily stem CO₂ fluxes, although ten times lower than the soil fluxes per unit area,
574 showed no interdependence with the surrounding soil, suggesting that most of the CO₂ emitted by
575 the stem originated from the respiratory metabolism within the tree (CO₂ locally respired or
576 transported from lower tree locations) rather than from soil and rhizospheric sources. Furthermore,
577 regardless of the seasonal period (wet or dry), the subdaily patterns for CO₂ effluxes for soil and stems
578 were opposite in phase, with soil emissions decreasing from early morning on (Janssens *et al.*, 1998)
579 while stem emissions began to increase.

580 In addition, our experimental setup allowed us to quantitatively compare soil CO₂ efflux and root-
581 derived CO₂ transported through the xylem in a tropical forest. This commonly ignored flux pathway
582 for root-respired CO₂ can account for up to one-third of the below-ground CO₂ in temperate climates
583 (Aubrey & Teskey, 2009, 2021), leading to substantial misestimates of ecosystem carbon balances. In
584 agreement with previous studies (Aubrey & Teskey, 2009, 2021), our two tropical tree species showed
585 a substantial increase in dissolved CO₂ in the xylem sap at night (Fig. 6). This suggests that tree roots
586 and stems present substantial barriers that limit CO₂ diffusion and facilitate the build-up of CO₂ in the
587 xylem sap in the absence of transpiration (Steppe *et al.*, 2007; Teskey *et al.*, 2008). Subsequently, the
588 CO₂ dissolved in the xylem sap decreased during the morning as sap flow increased, partially because
589 CO₂ had lower solubility in water with increasing temperatures. The root-to-xylem CO₂ flux was quite
590 different between trees Ef and Lp. Overall, the amount of root-respired CO₂ entering the transpiration
591 stream via the roots was 1/6 and 1/33, for Ef and Lp, respectively, of the amount diffused into the soil
592 (Table 2). This implies that underestimations of below-ground respiration due to tree-mediated CO₂
593 transport may be less of an issue in tropical forests; the case of Ef is more consistent with the 17%
594 underestimation found in a Eucalyptus plantation through isotopic labelling (Grossiord *et al.*, 2012).
595 As sap flow was higher during the non-limited soil water periods, the transport of dissolved xylem CO₂
596 likely followed parallel seasonal variations. In any case, further studies on a larger number of tree
597 species and individuals are required to accurately compare the inter-tree and temporal variability of

598 root-derived CO₂ transported through the xylem with the soil CO₂ efflux, which to our knowledge is
599 reported here for the first time in a tropical forest.

600 4. Conclusion

601 There was no clear subdaily pattern for stem-emitted CH₄, although it varied considerably between
602 the trees and seasonal periods. In contrast, stem N₂O uptake and CO₂ emissions from Ef and Lp showed
603 similar subdaily patterns regardless of the period. In addition, correlations between subdaily patterns
604 of stem greenhouse gas fluxes and tree physiological variables were inconsistent. Albeit, our study
605 contributes to the general understanding of the environmental regulation of stem greenhouse gas
606 fluxes and shows that additional variables in stems and roots (e.g. internal gas concentrations, wood-
607 colonising microorganisms, wood density) and surrounding soils may account for the remaining
608 unexplained variability in stem fluxes. Therefore, and because our results may be site- and species-
609 specific, there is a critical need for further studies measuring greenhouse gas fluxes and possible
610 associated environmental drivers at high (or comparable) temporal resolutions on multiple trees, tree
611 species (e.g. from contrasting functional groups such as slow-growing trees vs. short-lived pioneer
612 species) and ecosystems (e.g. riparian forests, secondary forests and plantations). Our data
613 indisputably show that further experimental studies are essential to better describe, quantify and
614 integrate trees into the models for predicting CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ cycles. Significant modelling efforts
615 have incorporated tree stem CO₂ fluxes and similar efforts have been initiated for tree CH₄ fluxes
616 (Anttila *et al.*, 2023), but to our knowledge, this is not yet the case for N₂O fluxes. Our study provides
617 the first multi-year time series of continuous flux measurements combining the full range of stem
618 greenhouse gases and environmental variables in a hitherto overlooked forest ecosystem.

619

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639 AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

640 LMB, RLS, CS, IAJ planned and designed the research. LMB, CS, JYG, BB performed experiments,
 641 conducted fieldwork. LMB, RLS performed the quality control checks on the data and analysed the
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 643 contributed to the manuscript and gave final approval for submission.

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646 Non declared.

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858 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

859 **Fig. S1** Comparison between raw tree stem and soil carbon dioxide (CO₂) fluxes obtained with different
860 gas analysers.

861 **Fig. S2** Seasonal course of methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and carbon dioxide (CO₂) fluxes from
862 stem surfaces of the two studied tropical trees.

863 **Fig. S3** Seasonal course of methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and carbon dioxide (CO₂) fluxes from
864 soil surfaces surrounding the two studied tropical trees.

865 **Fig. S4** Seasonal course for daily mean sap flow rate, irreversible growth, stem water deficit, and CO₂
866 concentrations in the xylem of two tropical trees.

867 **Fig. S5** Short-term variations in sap flow rate and stem diameter of two tropical trees.

868 **Fig. S6** Daily mean values of tree stem and soil CH₄ fluxes in two stems and their surrounding soils in
869 a tropical forest.

870 **Fig. S7** Daily mean values of tree stem and soil N₂O fluxes in two stems and their surrounding soils in
871 a tropical forest.

872 **Fig. S8** Daily mean values of tree stem and soil CO₂ fluxes in two stems and their surrounding soils in
873 a tropical forest.

874 **Fig. S9** Photo of flammable gasses emitted from a tropical tree stem.

875